

Active surface area and intrinsic catalytic oxygen evolution reactivity of NiFe LDH at reactive electrode potentials using capacitances

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Abstract: Determination of the electrochemically active surface area (ECSA) is essential in electrocatalysis to provide surface normalized intrinsic catalytic activity. Conventionally, ECSAs of metal oxides and hydroxides are estimated using double layer capacitance (C_{dl}) measured at non-faradaic potential windows. However, in the case of Ni-based hydroxide catalysts for the oxygen evolution reaction (OER), the non-faradaic potential region before the Ni(II) oxidation peak is non-conductive, which hinders accurate electrochemical measurements. To overcome this problem, in this work, we have investigated the use of electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) at reactive OER potentials to extract the capacitance that is hypothesized to arise due to reactive OER intermediates (O^* , OH^* , OOH^*) adsorbed on the catalyst surface. This allowed the estimation of ECSA and intrinsic activity of NiFe layered double hydroxide (NiFe LDH), the most active, state of the art OER electrocatalyst in alkaline media. We analyzed the OER adsorbates capacitance (C_a) on NiFe LDH and $Ni(OH)_2$ at different electrode potentials and identified a suitable potential range for

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accurate ECSA evaluation. Finally, we validated our method and the choice of potential range through rigorous catalyst loading and support studies.

Keywords: layered double hydroxide (LDH), NiFe, electrochemically active surface area (ECSA), electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS)

1. INTRODUCTION

Hydrogen production by water electrolysis using surplus renewable electricity is a promising strategy for solving the intermittency problem related to renewable energy resources¹ Among various water electrolysis technologies, alkaline water electrolysis and proton-exchange membrane (PEM) water electrolysis are two of the most established systems for this purpose.² While alkaline water electrolysis, which usually consists of Ni-based electrodes immersed in a highly concentrated alkaline electrolyte, is the most mature system among water electrolysis, it has poor hydrogen production efficiency compared to PEM water electrolysis due to high system resistance resulting from its non-compact system design.³ On the other hand, PEM water electrolysis has significantly higher hydrogen production rate due to the compact membrane-electrode assembly (MEA) architecture, but its acidic operating condition limits the electrocatalysts to consist of precious metals such as platinum or iridium.⁴ Therefore, attempts to improve hydrogen production rate while maintaining the use of non-platinum group metal (PGM) based electrocatalysts have sparked the development of anion exchange membrane (AEM) water electrolysis, which has a MEA architecture that operates in an alkaline condition.⁵

In water electrolysis, oxygen evolution reaction (OER) acts as a limiting reaction due to high overpotentials.⁶ In order to improve the hydrogen production rate of AEM water electrolysis while maintaining the low cost of materials, development of highly active non-PGM OER electrocatalysts is necessary. Among many electrocatalysts, NiFe layered double hydroxide (NiFe LDH) is generally accepted as the most active OER catalyst in an alkaline medium.⁷ Therefore, large amount of research has been conducted to understand the origin of its high activity, as well as to further improve its activity through various strategies such as composition control, morphology control and supporting the catalyst with conductive

materials.⁸⁻¹¹

When evaluating the performance of electrocatalysts, one of the most important benchmark parameters to consider is electrochemically active surface area (ECSA) of the material, as it is required for the calculation of surface-normalized intrinsic activity.^{12, 13} Conventionally, ECSAs of metal oxides and hydroxides are estimated using double layer capacitance (C_{dl}) measured by cyclic voltammetries (CV) at non-faradaic region, as suggested by Jaramillo et al.¹⁴ However, in the case of Ni-based hydroxides, it is well established that the catalysts are non-conductive at the non-faradaic potential region before the Ni(II) oxidation.¹⁵ (Figure 1a) This makes the electrochemical measurements taken in this region to be unreliable.¹⁶ While the measurement of C_{dl} in the non-faradaic region between the redox peak and the onset potential at which OER occurs might be feasible for some catalysts, it is not possible for some highly active Ni-based hydroxide OER catalysts, such as for NiFe LDH, as OER currents may overlap with the Ni(II) oxidation peak.¹⁷

In order to solve this problem, many researches have been focused on developing other reliable methods for quantification of the ECSA of Ni-based hydroxides. For example, several authors suggested the use of electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) at potentials above the Ni(II) oxidation peak and used different equivalent circuits to extract either the C_{DL} or capacitances associated to other processes.^{16, 18-21} This analysis was also combined with other kinetics analysis,^{18, 19} or compared with other methods. For example, Batchellor et al. discussed and compared the extracted C_{DL} to the integral of the charge passed during the oxidation and reduction of redox active Ni in their electrodeposited film and found a linear relation. However, the majority of the previous studies have only been carried out on electrodeposited films and none in the form of nanoparticles, another widely utilized morphology of electrocatalysts.

Herein, in order to calculate the ECSA of NiFe LDH in the form of nanoparticles, we propose performing electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) at OER active potential, which will allow us to calculate the adsorbate capacitance (C_a) arising due to OER intermediate species (O^* , OH^* , OOH^*) on the active sites of NiFe LDH, as recently proposed in the literature.^{10, 20} We note that the idea of measuring C_a from EIS has been reported in the past in a few works.²¹⁻²³ However, a specific capacitance value for translating the C_a of Ni-based

hydroxides to ECSA has only been provided recently²⁴ and intensive verification of such method has not been carried out yet. This method is beneficial in the sense that the capacitance is measured during the reaction, when the catalyst is electrically conductive, and that only the capacitance from the active component of the catalyst rather than the support material is accounted for. To understand the behavior of C_a , EIS measurements were taken and interpreted at a wide range of potentials: from the region before the Ni^{2+} oxidation feature up to potentials at which the OER geometric current density reached a few mA cm^{-2} . The ECSA of catalysts were then calculated by taking the value of C_a calculated from EIS fitting at a chosen range of OER active potential, then dividing it by the specific OER adsorbate capacitance (C_s), which is reported in the literature for $\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2$.²⁰ The choice of range of potential for ECSA calculation and applicability of this method is validated by rigorous catalyst loading study and support study. The results show that this method is able to take into account contributions to the catalytic activity that are due to increase in surface areas, providing surface-normalized intrinsic catalytic activities.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1 Synthesis of NiFe LDHs

Synthesis of NiFe LDH was carried out following the method from a previous publication.²⁵ First, nickel(II) acetate tetrahydrate (79.6 mg) and iron(III) nitrate nonahydrate (25.8 mg) were hydrolyzed in deionized water separately (2.4 mL and 1.6 mL, respectively, Ni:Fe = 5:1).

The precursor solutions were added to a mixed solution of deionized water (30 mL) & dimethylformamide (DMF) (16 mL) in autoclave liner and sonicated for 5 min. The solvothermal reaction was then performed at 130 °C for 16 hours, followed by additional solvothermal reaction at 170 °C for 2 hours. The autoclave was naturally cooled down, and the obtained suspension was ultrasonicated and washed with a centrifuge 2 times in deionized water and ethanol mixture, followed by 2 times in pure deionized water. The sample was then freeze dried overnight. A yellowish-orange powder was obtained.

2.2 Synthesis of Ni(OH)₂

Synthesis of Ni(OH)₂ was carried out following the method from a previous publication.²⁶ Ni(OH)₂ was synthesized using a two-step synthesis consisting of a precipitation step and a hydrothermal treatment afterwards.

First, nickel(II) acetate tetrahydrate (106.6 mg) was dissolved in deionized water (50 ml) in an autoclave-glass. To precipitate the Ni(OH)₂ nanoparticles, 1 M KOH (1 mL) solution was added. The reaction solution was stirred for 10 min and then handed in a glass lined steel autoclave. The solution was heated during the hydrothermal treatment for 16 hours at 130 °C, followed by 2 hours at 170 °C. The autoclave was naturally cooled down, and the obtained suspension was ultrasonicated and washed with a centrifuge 2 times in deionized water and ethanol mixture, followed by 2 times in pure deionized water. The sample was then freeze dried overnight. A light green powder was obtained.

2.3 Catalyst ink and electrode preparation

Glassy carbon (GC) disks (5 mm diameter) were polished manually with a 5 μm and 0.05 μm micropolish alumina suspension for ~3 min each treatment using a nylon and microcloth

polishing pads, respectively, before each catalyst coating. After polishing, the disks were cleaned three times by ultrasonication in water, acetone, and water and finally dried with a nitrogen flow. 1600 μl isopropanol, 400 μl of pure water and 5 μl Nafion solution (5 wt%) was added to 1.97 mg of the catalyst powder. In the case of support study, Ketjen-black EC600JD was added (0.22 mg for 10 wt%, 0.49 mg for 20 wt%) during the ink preparation.

The catalyst ink solution was sonicated for 20 min with a 1/8 inch microtip sonifier. Then a specified volume of the ink was pipetted on the polished glassy carbon (GC) electrode surface depending on the intended loading of the catalyst, i.e. 4 μl for 0.02 $\text{mg}_{\text{NiFe LDH}}/\text{cm}^2$ or 20 μl for 0.1 $\text{mg}_{\text{NiFe LDH}}/\text{cm}^2$. The electrode was then dried in a convection oven for 10 min at 60 °C.

2.4 RDE measurements

Electrochemical experiments were performed in a three-compartment glass cell using a potentiostat (Gamry) at room temperature. The working electrode consisted of the catalyst coated GC electrode mounted on the head of a rotating shaft. A Pt-mesh and a Hydroflex reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE, Gaskatel) were used as a counter electrode and a reference electrode, respectively. The counter electrode was separated from the working electrode compartment by a fine-porosity glass frit, and a Luggin capillary was used for the reference electrode. The reference electrode was controlled regularly in comparison to a polycrystalline Pt disk under H_2 bubbling, but no corrections were necessary, confirming the proper functioning of the RHE.

In order to resolve the high frequency artifacts arising during EIS measurements, a shunt capacitor with a capacitance value of 4.2 μF was connected between the reference electrode and an additional Pt wire with its end located near the opening of the Luggin capillary.²⁷

0.1 M KOH electrolyte was prepared with KOH pellets (semiconductor grade, 99.99% trace metals basis, Aldrich), and MilliQ water. For RDE measurements involving $\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2$, the electrolyte was purified by using sacrificial $\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2$ according to the procedure described by Boettcher et al. to remove Fe impurities.¹⁵ NiFe LDH was tested without further Fe purification of the electrolyte, since residual Ni ions introduced during the purification can possibly influence its activity, and it already contains Fe.

All electrochemical measurements were carried out in N₂-saturated 0.1 M KOH and under rotation of RDE at 1600 rpm. For loading study and support study, the RDE measurement was repeated at least 3 times on multiple electrodes to confirm the consistency of the measurement. The current density values reported are normalized by the geometric area of the GC electrode (0.196 cm²), except for intrinsic current density, which was normalized by the calculated ECSA instead. Internal resistance (iR) correction was conducted manually after the measurements using the value of resistance obtained during electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS). All the potentials reported are iR-corrected, unless otherwise stated.

2.5 Electrochemical protocol

The catalyst was first introduced under open circuit potential (OCP) in the N₂ saturated 0.1 M KOH electrolyte for 1 min. Chronoamperometry (CA) at OCP was then applied for 1 min to let the current stabilize. Then, potentiostatic electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (PEIS) was applied at OCP to evaluate the solution resistance for the iR-correction. Following the PEIS, cyclic voltammetry (CV) was conducted as an activation treatment of the catalyst for 50 cycles at the scan rate of 50 mV s⁻¹. To ensure sufficient activation, CV was conducted from a resting potential to a highly active potential (from 1.0 V_{RHE} to 1.7 V_{RHE} for NiFe LDH, and from 1.0 V_{RHE} to 1.9 V_{RHE} for Ni(OH)₂).

After the CV, the catalyst activity was evaluated by linear sweep voltammetry (LSV) from 1.20 V_{RHE} to 1.75 V_{RHE} at a scan rate of 1 mV s⁻¹. Resting at OCP for 180 s and a PEIS measurement were carried out before LSV to control the value of the solution resistance.

After the LSV, EIS measurements for the purpose of calculating C_a (and ECSA consequently) were conducted using multiple PEISs. CA was held for 30 seconds right before each PEIS measurement at the same potential to ensure steady-state of current before PEIS. When investigating the behavior of OER adsorbates, the potential ranges for PEIS measurements were 1.40 V_{RHE} – 1.70 V_{RHE} for NiFe LDH, and 1.30 V_{RHE} – 1.80 V_{RHE} for Ni(OH)₂. When quantifying the C_a for ECSA calculation, the potential range for PEIS measurements was 1.55 V_{RHE} – 1.65 V_{RHE} for both NiFe LDH and Ni(OH)₂.

All PEIS measurements in this work were carried out using a probing signal amplitude of 10

mV, with frequency range between 100 kHz – 2 Hz, with 16 points taken per each decade of frequency range. EIS data obtained was analyzed using EIS Data Analysis 1.3 software.²⁸

2.6 Characterizations

X-ray diffraction (XRD; D8 Advance, Bruker) with Cu K-alpha was used to identify the crystal structure of Ni(OH)₂ and NiFe LDH. Field emission-transmission electron microscope (FE-TEM) and energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) (Talos F200X, FEI) was used at 200 kV to evaluate the shape and size of Ni(OH)₂ and NiFe LDH. Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer (ICP-MS; iCAP RQ) was used to find the actual content of Ni and Fe atoms in NiFe LDH.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Methodology

Figure 1. Oxygen evolution reaction (OER) mechanism and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) analysis method for Ni-based materials. (a) Schematic representation of OER intermediates on the surface of NiFe LDH before and after α -to- γ phase transition on glassy carbon electrode or an inert support. Only one type of OER intermediate (*OH) is shown for simplicity of the model (b) Typical Nyquist plot obtained from EIS measurement of Ni-based hydroxide material at OER active potential. (c) Equivalent circuit model used to fit Nyquist plot of OER in this work. The model includes uncompensated solution resistance (R_u), charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}), double layer capacitance represented using constant-phase element (CPE_{dl}), OER adsorbates resistance (R_a) and OER adsorbates capacitance represented using constant-phase element (CPE_a).

NiFe LDH is a state of art OER catalyst in alkaline medium, but the exact OER mechanisms on NiFe LDH and its Fe-free analog Ni(OH)₂ are still under debate.^{26, 29, 30} However, in alkaline medium, a popular mechanism for the oxygen evolution reaction (OER) follows the simple scheme:³¹

In this case, three OER intermediates (*OH, *O and *OOH) are adsorbed onto the active surface of the catalyst and are in dynamic equilibrium with each other. As the intermediates are charged species, adsorption and desorption of these intermediates are interfacial charge transfer processes, which result in an electric current. Therefore, the amount of this current is proportional to the amount of coverage of the catalyst surface by the adsorbates, which is dependent on the perturbation of the applied potential. As discussed by Watzele et al., this can be represented in equation as $C_a = q \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial E}$, where C_a is a capacitance that arises due to adsorbed OER intermediates (which is labeled “OER adsorbates capacitance”) while q represents charge associated with a complete adsorbate layer, θ represents fraction of surface coverage by OER intermediates and E represents applied potential.²⁰

Fortunately, this C_a can be decoupled from the C_{dl} through fitting of electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurement spectra. An example of EIS spectra, which is taken at the OER active potential for a Ni-based hydroxide material, is shown in Figure 1b. Such EIS spectra can be fitted using the equivalent circuit shown in Figure 1c, which

represents a physical model for the adsorption of a single intermediate.²² Although the OER mechanism described above involves three intermediates, at a sufficiently low overpotential where reaction begins to take place, we can assume only one OER intermediate is quasi-reversible. Furthermore, due to the presence of complex potential-dependent electrochemical and structural transformations in Ni-based (oxy)hydroxides, as well as the possibility of ions moving in and out of the interface region as holes are placed on and off the catalytically active phase, the hypothesis that the extracted capacitance is related to the OER adsorbate intermediates needs to be verified. While advanced spectroscopic methods might be required for a definitive validation of this hypothesis, we believe that the combination of electrochemical and impedance spectroscopy analysis as a function of applied potentials is able to provide valuable insights on the applicability, advantages and limitations of the proposed method to assess the ECSA. In this work, we will validate this methodology for the case of NiFe LDH and its Fe-free analog hydroxide Ni(OH)₂ with nanoplatelet catalyst morphology, in contrast to previously investigated thin film model electrodes, and in the presence and absence of additional support.

3.2 Characterization of NiFe LDH and Ni(OH)₂

In order to study the behavior of OER adsorbates on NiFe LDH, highly crystalline NiFe LDH and its Fe-free analog hydroxide Ni(OH)₂ were synthesized following a previously reported solvothermal method in DMF/H₂O mixture.^{25, 26}

Based on the X-ray diffraction (XRD) pattern (Figure S1), NiFe LDH and Ni(OH)₂ show only the intended phase. The sharp (003) peak of NiFe LDH and (001) peak of Ni(OH)₂ indicates the layered structure of these hydroxides. Additionally, the peak pattern shows that Ni(OH)₂ was prepared as β -phase. The size and morphology of NiFe LDH and Ni(OH)₂ are characterized using transmission electron microscopy (TEM). (Figure S2a, S2b) The NiFe LDH has a hexagonal platelet morphology with a size of ~ 400 nm in diameter. The edges are slightly damaged, probably due to sonication process used to disperse catalysts during the TEM sample preparation. The TEM images also indicate the presence of FeO_x nanoparticles, which are formed unavoidably from the solvothermal reaction in DMF/H₂O mixture solvent. However, based on the TEM images, the amount is minimal compared to bulk NiFe LDH, and so it is expected to have negligible contribution to the ECSA calculation of NiFe LDH.

On the other hand, Ni(OH)₂ had a round platelet morphology with a size of ~ 50 nm in diameter. The amount of Fe atoms in comparison to Ni atoms in NiFe LDH are measured using inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS). (Table S1) ICP-MS indicates that the percentage of Fe in NiFe LDH was 16.7 %, which is only 0.6 % different from the precursor percentage of 17.3% (Ni:Fe atomic ratio of 5:1), implying that the synthesis of catalysts have been carried out as intended.

3.3 Behavior of OER adsorbates capacitance on NiFe LDH and Ni(OH)₂ surfaces at different potentials

Figure 2. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) analysis of NiFe LDH and Ni(OH)₂. Pseudocapacitance value of CPE_a at a wide range of applied potentials obtained from fitting of Nyquist plots and linear sweep voltammetry at a scan rate of 1 mV s⁻¹ for (a) NiFe LDH and (b) Ni(OH)₂. The error bars indicate quality of fitting using the equivalent

circuit model and the pseudocapacitances are attributed to different processes based on the applied potential regions. Nyquist plots for (c) NiFe LDH and (d) Ni(OH)₂. Nyquist plots of (e) NiFe LDH and (f) Ni(OH)₂ enlarged at the high frequency region to highlight the number of capacitive elements. The catalyst loading was 0.1 mg cm⁻², the catalysts were unsupported.

To understand the behavior of C_a on NiFe LDH, EIS measurements were taken at a wide range of potential from non-faradaic region to OER active potential. At non-faradaic region, 1.40 V_{RHE} - 1.42 V_{RHE}, C_a does not appear, since there is no adsorption of intermediates on the surface of non-conductive and inactive as-prepared α -phase NiFe LDH. (Figure 2a) Nyquist plot of EIS measurement taken in this region, at 1.42 V_{RHE}, show a single semi-circle which indicates clearly that there is only one capacitive element in the system; C_{dl}. (Figure 2c, 2e)

At potential around 1.43 V_{RHE}, a redox peak involving oxidation of Ni species appears in LSV. It was previously shown that the redox feature is associated with partial transition of as-prepared non-conductive α -phase NiFe LDH into conductive γ -phase NiFe LDH, which is the phase with active catalytic surface.²⁶ In alkaline KOH electrolyte, the transition involves deprotonation of the hydroxyls of α -phase NiFe LDH, which breaks the hydrogen bonds between them. As bond breakage happens, previously favored intercalated CO₃²⁻ is expelled and K⁺ ions and H₂O molecules from the alkaline electrolyte are newly intercalated as α -to- γ phase transition occurs. Since this redox process involves multiple chemical processes, associated pseudocapacitances might appear in the redox region and overlap with the rise of the C_a. Fitting the EIS spectra in this region using the proposed equivalent circuit produces apparent C_a larger than the expected values, since the circuit does not disentangle the two contributions. This also results in large errors during fitting of Nyquist plots using the equivalence circuit. In other words, the proposed equivalent circuit does not represent a physical model for the system in this potential region, which requires a more complex model.

This phenomenon is supported by the appearance of a “loop” at the low frequency region of the Nyquist plot at 1.43 V_{RHE}, which is the potential at which the redox process begins to take place. (Figure 2c) This phenomenon occurs when impedance spectroscopy measurement is taken at a transient/non-equilibrium state.³² Since the transition from α -to- γ phase is only partial and limited, especially at lower potential of redox region, there is still a large proportion of non-conductive α -phase. Thus, we speculate that the accumulated charge in the

conductive γ -phase cannot be dissipated quickly enough during EIS measurement, resulting in non-equilibrium transient state. This causes a phase shift between voltage and current, resulting in a non-linear current response.

From 1.44 V_{RHE} onwards, two semi-circles appear in the Nyquist plot, indicating an additional capacitive element in the system apart from the C_{dl} , which is C_a . (Figure 2e) With increase in applied potential, the decrease in the size of the semi-circle is observed, which implies that charge transfer resistance is decreasing. At sufficiently high potential around 1.50 V_{RHE} , OER starts to take place, which is followed by the plateau of C_a , implying the saturation of the catalytically active surface with the reaction intermediate species. However, this trend is different from the results reported by Watzele et al., which showed that majority of OER catalysts generally had an increase in C_a until it reaches a plateau at the onset of OER, where it is locally independent of the applied potential.²⁰ We believe that the discrepancy arises due to the difference in total exposed surface area of catalyst. The catalyst layers tested in this work are in the form of porous layers of solution-casted nanoparticles, while the catalysts tested by Watzele et al., were prepared in the form of electrodeposited thin films. This would result in a vast difference in the amount of pseudocapacitance in the redox region. (Figure 2a) To investigate further this rise in pseudocapacitance and its association with the Ni redox processes, we carried out a similar investigation for NiFe LDH's Fe-free analog hydroxide, Ni(OH)_2 .

Ni(OH)_2 has a very similar layered structure with NiFe LDH, and also has OER activity in alkaline medium.³³ However, compared to NiFe LDH, Ni(OH)_2 's redox process occurs at lower potential, and the overpotential for OER is much higher. (Figure S3) Therefore, Ni(OH)_2 provides a large window of potential at which we can investigate the behavior of C_a before the onset of OER.

According to Bode cycle, for OER to occur, anhydrous β -phase Ni(OH)_2 is eventually transformed to overcharged hydrous γ -phase NiOOH under anodic potential and after charging to an intermediate β - NiOOH phase.^{34, 35} Similar to NiFe LDH, the γ -phase formation process is also speculated to involve deprotonation and intercalation of various species such as K^+ and H_2O .³⁶ We note that the phase transformations in Ni(OH)_2 are much more complex than in NiFe LDH, i.e. the Bode diagram involves four limiting phases,³³ and

their detailed description and correlation with the pseudocapacitance is beyond the scope of this manuscript. Nonetheless, a sharp increase in apparent pseudocapacitance after a “loop” at the low frequency region of the Nyquist plot appears at 1.40 V_{RHE} , which is the start of redox potential, confirming what observed for NiFe LDH. (Figure 2b, 2d and 2f) In the case of Ni(OH)₂, the pseudocapacitance drops until a plateau is reached at the onset of OER around 1.58 V_{RHE} . The pseudocapacitance remains approximately the same until blockage of active sites due to formation of oxygen bubbles on the surface of catalysts occurs at a high potential around 1.72 V_{RHE} ~ 1.80 V_{RHE} (Figure 2b). Finally, by the comparison of the two Ni-based catalysts we conclude that the rise of the pseudocapacitance to higher values than the ones expected for the capacitance of adsorbed OER intermediates is associated to Ni redox processes. In the conditions explored in this study, this does not preclude the formation of a potential region with a stable value for the capacitance. Further studies are required to evaluate at what experimental conditions this effect limits the ECSA evaluation.

3.4 ECSA determination and intrinsic activities of NiFe LDH and Ni(OH)₂

To determine ECSA of NiFe LDH and Ni(OH)₂ nanoparticles, we need a range of potential at which the pseudocapacitance can reliably represent the C_a solely, and a value of OER adsorbate capacitance for a flat surface of the same material obtained within that range (specific capacitance, C_s).

In order to reliably choose a range of potential for ECSA calculation, we need to consider a few criteria. Obviously, the range of potential should be chosen at potential higher than that of the Ni redox peak since both Ni-based hydroxide materials do not have sufficient electrical conductivity before the phase transition takes place. From our study of behavior of C_a , the range chosen should not be too close to the redox peak either, as pseudocapacitance arising from various chemical processes such as deprotonation and intercalation during the phase transition can cause apparent C_a to seem higher than the actual value. Yet, the range of potential chosen should correspond to low OER current, as the equivalent circuit model is applied under an assumption that the surface concentration of reactant is similar to that of bulk,²⁰ and bubble accumulation on the surface of the catalyst can occur at high current, covering the active sites. Most importantly, the range of potential should be taken at a region where the pseudocapacitance has reached a steady-state, implying full coverage of active

sites by OER adsorbates. Additionally, a range of potential at which good fitting of impedance spectra can be achieved with the equivalence circuit model is preferred, since it signifies that the model is a good representation of physical phenomena occurring at that potential. Based on the above criteria, we believe that pseudocapacitance at a potential range of $1.58 V_{\text{RHE}} - 1.62 V_{\text{RHE}}$ best represents C_a for both NiFe LDH and Ni(OH)₂.

In the case of specific capacitance, we used the C_s values provided by Bandarenka and coworkers for a flat NiO_x film in 0.1 M KOH, which is around $300 \mu\text{F cm}^{-2}$. Since the measurement was carried out in strong alkaline medium, the outermost surface of the film is expected to be chemically similar to our synthesized Ni(OH)₂ nanoparticles. Ideally, for different materials, i.e. Ni(OH)₂ and NiFe LDH, a different specific capacitance should be used. Watzele et al. calculated a specific capacitance of $300 \pm 99 \mu\text{F cm}^{-2}$ for electrodeposited NiO_x and $430 \pm 160 \mu\text{F cm}^{-2}$ for electrodeposited NiFeO_x.²⁰ The preparation of atomically flat surfaces of defined geometry for these materials remains challenging, and corrections for roughness are necessary, i.e. by atomic force microscopy. More studies of this type will be important for the further development of the method and validation of the specific capacitance values of different materials. However, the main focus of the current work is not the comparison between the two catalysts, since it is very well known and widely accepted that NiFe LDH is more active than Ni(OH)₂, but rather on the verification of the methodology suggested in this work. Therefore, for simplicity, we assume the value for $300 \mu\text{F cm}^{-2}$ for both catalysts. We once again do acknowledge that this value is very large compared to other more commonly used specific capacitance values, such $80 \mu\text{F cm}^{-2}$ from the work by Batchellor et al.,¹⁶ or $40 \mu\text{F cm}^{-2}$ from the work by McCrory et al.¹⁴, which were used in their work to normalize double layer capacitances.

By normalizing the calculated C_a of NiFe LDH and Ni(OH)₂ with the C_s , the ECSAs of NiFe LDH and Ni(OH)₂ are found to be 0.611 cm^2 and 1.236 cm^2 , respectively, at 0.1 mg cm^{-2} catalyst loading. (Figure **S4b**) At this loading, the ECSAs normalized by mass of catalysts are $3.11 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ and $6.29 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ respectively for NiFe LDH and Ni(OH)₂. The obtained values for ECSAs are expected to be low due to poor dispersion and agglomeration of bulk nanoparticles without any support materials. The poor dispersion results in low electrochemical accessibility of electrolyte to the majority of component of the catalyst, inhibiting transition from non-conductive and inactive phase to conductive and active

phase.³⁷ By normalizing the OER current with calculated ECSA, we obtained intrinsic activity of both NiFe LDH and Ni(OH)₂ (Figure S4c). In each case, the overpotential required at intrinsic current density of 0.1 mA cm⁻²_{ECSA} were 403 mV for Ni(OH)₂ and 272 mV for NiFe LDH, showing the superior intrinsic activity of NiFe LDH as expected.

3.5 NiFe LDH loading study

Figure 3. NiFe LDH loading study. (a) OER adsorbates capacitance, (b) ECSAs, (c) geometric current densities and (d) intrinsic current densities of unsupported NiFe LDH at various catalyst loading. All electrochemical measurements were carried out in purified 0.1 M KOH by glassy carbon rotating disk electrode (RDE) at 1600 r.p.m. The current densities are obtained by linear sweep voltammetry at a scan rate of 1 mV s⁻¹. The measurement for each loading was repeated 3 times to ensure reliability of the data.

Although the calculation of ECSA through the above method is not new, a proper validation of its applicability to nanoparticle electrocatalysts has not been conducted before. In order to validate the method, and the choice of range of potential for ECSA calculation, we carried out a loading study for unsupported bulk NiFe LDH. The amount of catalyst on the glassy carbon electrode was carefully controlled to 0.025, 0.050, 0.075, 0.100 and 0.125 mg cm⁻² respectively, and the test for each loading amount was repeated 3 times to ensure reliability of

the results. (Figure S5) When the amount of NiFe LDH on the catalyst is very low (0.025 and 0.050 mg cm⁻²), linear relationship between the loading amount and C_a were observed, implying high utilization of the catalyst. (Figure 3a and S6) As the loading amount of NiFe LDH increased, the C_a started to become saturated, implying a limited utilization of catalyst. While this trend is anticipated, it was surprising to observe such phenomenon at catalyst loading lower than 0.1 mg cm⁻², which is around the recommended amount of catalyst loading for study of OER catalyst on glassy carbon electrode.³⁸ By normalizing the calculated OER adsorbates capacitances by the specific capacitance, the average of ECSAs for each loading were obtained to be 0.242 cm⁻², 0.461 cm⁻², 0.528 cm⁻², 0.567 cm⁻², 0.596 cm⁻² respectively. (Figure 3b) Corresponding to the C_a trend, the ECSA increases with catalyst loading amount.

Since the ECSAs increase with the loading amount of the same catalyst, the geometrical current densities subsequently increase with the loading amount of the catalyst too. (Figure 3c) The OER current densities for each catalyst loading are normalized by the obtained ECSA values to achieve intrinsic current densities. (Figure S7) When drawn together on the same axis, the intrinsic current densities overlapped notably well with each other, indicating that the method and the choice of range of potential is adequate for NiFe LDH. (Figure 3d) Since the catalyst used in this study is the same, the method shows that the activity enhancement is only due to the increased ECSA and not to higher intrinsic activity, confirming the expected behavior and proving its validity.

To further illustrate the benefit of the calculation of ECSAs using OER adsorbates capacitances, we additionally carried out ECSA calculation by measuring double layer capacitances using cyclic voltammetry in non-faradaic region at various NiFe LDH loading, following the protocol introduced by McCrory et al.¹⁴ (Figure S8 and Figure S9) The apparent double layer capacitance obtained using cyclic voltammetry did not show dependence on the loading amount of NiFe LDH. (Figure S10) Batchellor et al. saw very similar trends in electrodeposited NiFe (oxy)hydroxide film on Au electrode and FTO glass, where they explained that the double layer capacitance measured in the potential range where the catalyst is insulating comes from the conductive substrate, and not from the poorly conductive catalytic material.¹⁶ We believe that similar phenomenon is taking place for our NiFe LDH nanoparticles on glassy carbon electrode, showing the limitation of the method,

making it unsuitable in determining ECSA for Ni-based hydroxide catalysts. This further proves the superiority of method using measurement of OER adsorbates capacitances for determination of ECSA.

Another suggested method in calculation of ECSA of Ni-based hydroxide catalysts is to integrate the pre-OER Ni oxidation and reduction peaks, which is known to have linear relationship with loading of the electrodeposited catalyst film measured from quartz crystal microbalance (QCM).¹⁶ We similarly carried out integration of both Ni oxidation and reduction peak to investigate this for NiFe LDH nanoparticles. **(Figure S11)** We found that the mole of electrons calculated from both Ni oxidation peak and Ni reduction peak increased as NiFe LDH catalyst loading increased, similar to the trend observed for ECSA measured from OER adsorbate capacitance as a function catalyst loading. **(Figure S12a)** Therefore, we plotted mole of electrons from Ni redox peaks as a function of ECSA and found a linear relationship between them. **(Figure S12b)** While this could imply that integration of redox peaks could be applicable to NiFe LDH nanoparticles as a method for calculating ECSA, it must be carried out with extensive care as the integrations of Ni oxidation and reduction peak are heavily affected by the quality of fitting of the baseline, which is difficult for NiFe LDH due to the overlap of the oxidation peak with oxygen evolution reaction current. Additionally, Ni redox peaks are often highly dependent on the “history” of the material, due to slow discharge of conductive active phase which becomes “trapped” in insulating domains,¹⁶ and can lead to high deviations depending on the previous electrochemical treatments.

3.6 NiFe LDH support study

Figure 4. NiFe LDH support study. (a) geometric current densities, (b) ECSAs, (c) intrinsic current densities and (d) Nyquist plot obtained at 1.60 V_{RHE} of unsupported and supported NiFe LDH. The catalyst loading was controlled to 0.020 mg of NiFe LDH per cm² of glassy carbon electrode to ensure equal amount of catalyst for both samples. For supported sample, the catalyst to carbon ratio was 80:20 by weight percentage. All electrochemical measurements were carried out in purified 0.1 M KOH by glassy carbon rotating disk electrode (RDE) at 1600 r.p.m. The current densities are obtained by linear sweep voltammetry at a scan rate of 1 mV s⁻¹. The measurement for each sample was repeated 3 times to ensure reliability of the data.

Another benefit of the OER adsorbates capacitance method lies in its ability to differentiate capacitance from active component and inactive component of catalyst. As OER intermediates are adsorbed only on the surface of active catalyst surface and not the inactive support surfaces, we can accurately calculate its ECSA even for a supported catalyst. To validate this, we carried out a “support study” by dispersing NiFe LDH together with carbon black (Ketjen-black EC600JD) during catalyst ink preparation. For supported catalyst samples, to ensure identical physical and chemical properties of the active component of the catalyst, physical mixing of carbon black is carried out instead of supporting NiFe LDH directly on carbon support during the synthesis.

Initially, the catalyst/carbon ratio is controlled to 80/20 by weight percentage for the supported sample. When the catalyst inks were loaded on glassy carbon electrode, the catalyst loading of NiFe LDH was controlled to 0.020 mg/cm² excluding the carbon component, ensuring equal amounts of NiFe LDH for both unsupported and supported samples. Despite low loading of catalyst, the supported sample shows much higher geometric OER current density compared to the unsupported sample. (Figure **4a**, **S13a** and **S13b**) The reason for increase in current density can be attributed to higher dispersion of catalysts and increased electrical conductivity in the catalyst layer.³⁹ The average value of ECSA of the supported sample is 1.565 cm², while that of the unsupported sample is around 0.146 cm². (Figure **4b**, **S13c** and **S13d**) The difference is more than 10-fold, indicating a highly limited transition of as-prepared non-conductive and inactive α -phase NiFe LDH into conductive and active γ -phase NiFe LDH without support material. When the total OER current densities are normalized by ECSA, the intrinsic current densities of supported and unsupported samples overlap exceptionally well, indicating the applicability of the method with high precision to supported NiFe LDH as well. (Figure **4c**, **S13e** and **S13f**)

On the other hand, when the catalyst loading of NiFe LDH is increased to 0.100 mg/cm² excluding the carbon component, the ECSA normalization of the method is no longer able to entirely compensate catalytic activity differences. When the catalyst/carbon ratio is controlled to 80/20 and 90/10 by weight percentage for the supported sample, the geometric OER current densities are much higher than the unsupported sample. (Figure **S14a**, **S15a**, **S15b** and **S15c**) However, a minimal difference in OER current densities between the samples with 10 and 20 wt% carbon was observed despite the varying amount of carbon. This implies that maximum dispersion of NiFe LDH is reached upon addition of carbon to 10 wt% of the catalyst layer. Interestingly, the average value of ECSA calculated for 10 wt% sample was 7.603 cm², slightly higher than that for 20 wt% sample, which had ECSA of 7.183 cm². (Figure **S14b**, **S15d**, **S15e** and **S15f**) While both values were significantly higher than that of the unsupported sample with ECSA of 0.726 cm² as expected, the deviation of ECSAs between 10 wt% sample and 20 wt% sample despite nearly equal geometric OER current densities led to contrasting intrinsic OER current densities. (Figure **S14c**, **S15g**, **S15h** and **S15i**) The reason for such deviation could possibly be attributed to poor mass transport of electrolyte to the surface of catalysts. At higher catalyst loading, the catalyst layer becomes

much thicker, especially for supported catalysts, where the total catalyst loading including the support exceeds 0.1 mg/cm^2 . Since the rate of oxygen evolution is higher for supported catalysts, the large amount of oxygen bubbles formed may not escape easily through the thick porous catalyst layer. This speculation is also supported by the poor quality of Nyquist plot obtained for highly loaded supported catalysts (Figure S14d) compared to that of lowly loaded supported catalysts. (Figure 4d) Additionally, the element of diffusion through a thicker catalyst layer is not considered in the equivalent circuit model, which may result in error during fitting of EIS measurement data. Therefore, to obtain ECSA with high accuracy for supported NiFe LDH catalyst with high loading, additional adjustments to the method and model seem necessary.

4. CONCLUSIONS

While electrochemically active surface area (ECSA) of metal oxides and hydroxides are conventionally estimated using the double layer capacitance (C_{dl}) measured at non-faradaic potential window, it is inapplicable for Ni-based hydroxides oxygen evolution reaction (OER) catalysts due to lack of conductivity in non-faradaic potential region before Ni(II) oxidation peak. In this work, to overcome this problem, ECSAs for NiFe LDH and its Fe-free analog Ni(OH)₂ are measured using the OER adsorbate capacitance (C_a) calculated from the fitting of electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurement. EIS measurements were taken at a wide range of potential for NiFe LDH and Ni(OH)₂ nanoplatelet catalysts to gain understanding of behavior of C_a at different phases of the catalysts. For both NiFe LDH and Ni(OH)₂, no capacitance from OER adsorbates were observed at non-faradaic region. However, as the redox process occurred, multiple chemical processes led to the appearance of overlapped pseudocapacitances that are difficult to differentiate. As potential approached the onset of OER, the pseudocapacitance plateaued, implying full coverage of OER adsorbates on the active surface of NiFe LDH and Ni(OH)₂. By normalizing the C_a in this region by the specific OER adsorbate capacitance (C_s), we calculated the ECSA, which was then used to determine the intrinsic activities of NiFe LDH and Ni(OH)₂. In order to validate the method, rigorous catalyst loading and support study was carried out. When OER current densities of unsupported NiFe LDH at various loading were normalized by respective ECSAs and drawn together on the same axis, the intrinsic current densities overlapped notably well with each other, verifying the applicability of the method for NiFe LDH. Additionally, when the OER

current of supported NiFe LDH was normalized by ECSA calculated by C_a , it showed equal intrinsic activity as unsupported catalyst, demonstrating the ability to differentiate capacitances arising due to the active component of catalyst layer from the inactive component. Although further improvement may be required at high loading of supported NiFe LDH, our results collectively show the ability of C_a to accurately be translated to ECSA, which can be used to determine the intrinsic activity of both unsupported and supported NiFe LDH catalysts. This method and results will be of great use in benchmarking the activity of newly developed NiFe LDH-based electrocatalysts in the future.

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge on the ACS Publications website. The Supporting Information includes XRD, TEM images and ICP-MS results of Ni(OH)₂ and NiFe LDH, as well as additional electrochemical analysis including cyclic voltammetry, geometric current densities, apparent ECSA from OER adsorbates, double layer capacitances and redox current, and intrinsic current densities of unsupported and supported NiFe LDH.

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